

Research on Innovative Enrollment Marketing Strategy of Hunan Private Higher Vocational Colleges Based on Consumer Purchase Behavior

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Abstract

Under the situation of decreasing enrollment and fierce competition, private higher vocational colleges need to enhance their crisis awareness. Besides improving their own connotation construction, they should adjust their enrollment marketing strategies, use various enrollment methods, broaden enrollment channels and improve the enrollment quantity and quality. This paper analyzes another relationship among schools, students and parents from the perspective of consumers' purchasing behavior, taking students and parents as consumers, teaching and educating people in schools as products, applying the relevant theories of consumers' purchasing behavior, and developing integrated marketing with creative new 4Ps (products, channels, partners and publicity). Combining with the practical experience of private higher vocational colleges, this paper puts forward relevant innovative enrollment marketing strategies, which can provide some help for enrollment marketing of other colleges and universities.

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Introduction

1. Concept, Model and Decision of Consumer's Purchasing Behavior

1.1 concept

Consumer behavior, also known as consumer behavior, refers to all personal behaviors related to consumption that consumers take place around purchasing living materials. Including the psychological activities, physiological activities and other substantive activities displayed in the process of purchase or consumption from the formation of demand motivation to the occurrence of purchase behavior to the summary of post-purchase feelings^[1].

Fig. 1 Consumer buying behavior model

1.2 research model

Common patterns of studying consumer buying behavior are consumer buying behavior model (see Figure 1). It is a theoretical description of the causal relationship between all or partial variables involved in the

process of consumers' purchasing behavior. Including the stimulus-response model, Vibraye Ning model, Howard-Heath model, Hawkins consumer psychology and behavior model, etc. The stimulus-response model is the most basic one. Any consumer's purchase decision is driven by certain internal factors and stimulated by external factors. Through the model of consumers' purchasing behavior, we can see that consumers with certain potential needs are first stimulated by the marketing activities of enterprises and influenced by various external environmental factors to generate purchasing intentions; Consumers with different characteristics will make different responses to various external stimuli and influences based on specific internal factors and decision-making methods, thus forming different purchase orientations and purchase behaviors^[2]. Among them, the intrinsic factors of consumers' purchasing decisions mainly include motivation, demand, attitude, learning and so on. External factors design two kinds of related groups: one is participation group, which refers to the related groups in the consumer circle; One is the non-affiliated group, which refers to the group that is outside the circle but has an influence on the purchase.

1.3 the buyer decision process

Consumers' decision-making process is one of the important contents of consumers' buying behavior model. Understanding the content of this process is helpful to formulate appropriate promotion policies. This process is composed of many related activities, which starts before the purchase behavior and continues until after the purchase behavior. Enterprises (units) can take corresponding promotion measures according to the "thinking" of consumers' decision-making, only when they understand and master the purchasing decision-making process of consumers. Consumer decision-making process generally includes five stages, as shown in Figure 2 below. (1) cognitive problems. When consumers generate needs and desires, they will analyze and confirm their own needs and desires in their brains, and decide whether to take action and how to take action. (2) Collecting information. Consumers get information about commodities through individual, commercial, public and experience channels. (3) Evaluate alternatives. Think and analyze the obtained information and make a preliminary assessment. (4) Decision-making purchase. After the evaluation, the consumers finally expressed their purchase intention. (5) Post-purchase evaluation. It mainly includes the degree of satisfaction with various functions of goods after purchase and the attitude of re-consumption^[3].

Fig. 2 Characteristics corresponding to five stages of consumer behavior purchase decision

2. The Current Situation and Problems of Enrollment Marketing in Private Higher Vocational Colleges

2.1 status

At present, the marketing situation of Hunan private vocational colleges can be summarized as follows: the marketing model is unsystematic, the internal and external competition pressure is high, the quality of students is poor, and the marketing cost is high.

2.1.1 The marketing model has no system. Through visiting the directors of admissions offices of major private higher vocational colleges in Hunan, it is difficult for many schools to form an effective and fully supported enrollment marketing model because of the distribution relationship of enrollment marketing interests. Generally limited to the following ways: First, divide the responsible persons according to the enrollment areas, set up consultation points and contact teachers. Because the key student source market of private vocational schools is the middle and poor students of non-key high schools in the region, the enrollment personnel will go to the school for publicity at a fixed point, and contact the class teachers and students for publicity and marketing in advance; Second, adopt "home visit" publicity and marketing. Recruiters make a thorough survey of the target students in advance, and then contact the parents of the students through their home addresses, and conduct home visits and presentations to students and parents. Third, participate in various organizations' enrollment consultation meetings. Through the combination of education system and media, go to all senior high schools to give lectures in a unified time; Fourth, all kinds of online advertisements, Tik Tok,

Aauto Quicker, official website, WeChat official account and other channels publicize the school through animation, video and text, and put it into the advantages of the school to attract students and promote communication. In addition, the cover and front page of the college entrance examination guide for vocational colleges are also one of the publicity media that every school must contend for.

2.1.2 Great internal and external competition pressure. The social recognition of private higher vocational colleges is not high. Faced with the strong exclusion of public colleges, struggling for survival, it is difficult to recruit students, and it has become a shelter for some poor students. Due to various reasons such as the support of national policies and the precipitation of running history, the provincial public universities have obvious advantages in both running history and running quality. Some private higher vocational colleges, due to the trend of offline interests and false propaganda, have led to chaotic enrollment and difficult employment, which has brought bad influence to external enrollment marketing. In addition, high tuition fees have discouraged candidates and parents. There are very few foreign colleges and universities participating in the division of student source market, which is a dangerous signal and will become an important competitor of private higher vocational colleges in the future. Besides public colleges and foreign universities, there are homogenization competition, professional competition, tuition competition and employment competition in private higher vocational colleges, which also bring resistance to the enrollment of each school.

2.1.3 Poor quality of students. This is a chicken rib problem in private higher vocational colleges. From the external point of view of the school, one division can solve the problem of reading for most students with poor academic performance, while the other part of parents will regard the quality of students as an important reference criterion for choosing a school, and invisibly lose some high-quality students; Lower the recognition of off-campus peers and competent units. It will have an impact on the teaching, competition and other aspects in the later period of the school, leading to the loss of employment output and the overall brand of the school in the later period. However, in order to maintain the operation and development of private schools, we have to lower the entrance threshold in the enrollment process to solve the needs of parents of poor students in society and the survival of schools. In the later period, it is also an urgent problem for private higher vocational colleges to improve.

2.1.4 The marketing cost is high. Most private higher vocational colleges lack systematic, in-depth and thorough thinking and deployment before launching enrollment publicity activities. In addition, the publicity content is falsely exaggerated, the publicity target group is highly competitive, and the publicity channels are simple and rude, which not only fails to achieve the expected enrollment goals, but also consumes resources, especially the enrollment publicity expenses, travel expenses and introduction fees, resulting in high per capita marketing costs. According to incomplete statistics, the per capita enrollment cost of private higher vocational colleges is about 8 times higher than that of public higher vocational colleges.

2.2 exist problem

2.2.1 homogenization competition in marketing is serious, and there is no system or method.

(1) Due to the limitations of private higher vocational colleges, the person in charge of the admissions department is not from the marketing management class, which leads to the general lack of systematic enrollment marketing strategies in schools. Most schools have tinkered around with the traditional enrollment routines, without forming their own characteristics and integrating information and innovative means; (2) Simple and rude, with a weak sense of marketing and service; Not paying attention to the application of marketing theory in enrollment, ignoring the leading role of theory in practice.

2.2.2 Poor connotation, expensive tuition, difficult employment, exaggerated publicity and low brand influence.

(1) Faced with the crowding out of public colleges and the lack of support from policies and external funds, most private higher vocational colleges take enrollment as the top priority of the whole year, without paying attention to the building of internal core competitiveness, the establishment of brand culture, the improvement of student-centered teaching system and service marketing system. All the behaviors are just to fill the existing "free beds" in schools, which leads to obvious transaction orientation of enrollment^[4]. The tuition fees of private schools are expensive, which is understandable, but they should meet the needs of the market, such as ace majors, excellent talent training programs, matching excellent teachers and hardware experiment and training equipment, and high-quality employment prospects. (2) Students should not have the theory and skills of job responsibilities matching. Private higher vocational colleges should strengthen cooperation with external enterprises, set up specialties according to industries, build specialties on industries, and train available skilled talents for enterprises. This can not only solve the employment problem of school students, but also solve the talent demand problem of enterprises. In addition, it can also improve the specialty construction and teacher construction of schools, which is a good thing for all three parties to benefit. (3) In the process of enrollment marketing, due to the lack of training and management of enrollment personnel, the enrollment based on results and interests leads to false and exaggerated publicity of enrollment personnel, which has a serious impact on the brand of the school and leads to a vicious circle of enrollment. (4) Unstable teachers and no continuity of culture can not form brand influence. In addition to scientific management processes and advanced educational

concepts, a school needs a group of teachers who are strong in execution, dare to do things, dare to innovate and dare to fight hard. Compared with the teachers in public vocational colleges, in-service teachers in private schools are divided into two categories: one is old teachers who have retired from public schools; One is young teachers who have just graduated or have no experience. Compared with teachers in public colleges, the work quality and salary benefits of private higher vocational colleges are far from each other, especially for young teachers, which leads to teachers' low enthusiasm, low stability and low academic achievement. Old teachers' rich teaching experience and knowledge conservation also have no good environment for inheritance. The lack of passion, vitality and competitiveness in scientific research and teaching competitions in schools leads to the lack of competitiveness in teachers' brand and professional construction ability in private higher vocational colleges, and the inability to cultivate high-quality skilled talents.

Private higher vocational colleges should plan the development path of the school, strictly grasp the quality, continuously improve the connotation construction, strengthen the brand culture construction, strengthen the training of service marketing awareness, and strive to run private higher vocational colleges that are recognized by students, parents and society.

3. Marketing process analysis of enrollment

From the marketing point of view, private higher vocational colleges are the producers of vocational education, so students are the consumers of vocational education. For higher vocational colleges, its products are various skills training services for students, and the sales links are embodied in online and offline media communication and enrollment publicity [5]; For students, the five-year system, individual recruitment, volunteering for college entrance examination and other modes of study are like a consumption decision. We should make a decision-making purchase of this product in higher vocational schools according to our college entrance examination scores, personal hobbies, family background and other aspects.

As sellers, private higher vocational colleges should pay attention to the needs of buyers (students and parents), show the advantages and highlights of their own products, and adopt certain marketing methods to let "consumers" choose and "buy" themselves.

According to the five stages of purchasing decision-making of consumers' behavior, this paper analyzes them one by one (See figure 3. Marketing Mapping and Corresponding Edge of Enrollment).

Fig. 3 Marketing Mapping and Corresponding Edge of Enrollment

4. Innovative Integrated Marketing Mode in Private Higher Vocational Colleges

In the new era, the enrollment of private higher vocational colleges is also facing more challenges. First, the competition of similar private colleges is extremely fierce; Second, most students are occupied by public high-quality higher vocational colleges, and students and parents prefer public higher vocational colleges; Third, the enrollment cost becomes higher, and the source of students is the foundation of school development; Fourth, the loss of students is serious and the reputation of schools is poor. Based on the challenge, private higher vocational colleges should give full play to the advantages of "people-oriented", flexible mechanism, service-oriented, market demand-oriented and strive to promote characteristic vocational education.

From the perspective of marketing, private higher vocational colleges can take students as consumers and carry out integrated marketing with creative new 4Ps (products, channels, partners and publicity).

4.1 School internal marketing promotes and builds core competitiveness.

1. "Product-oriented" creativity, creating characteristic schools

Taking the school as a product and students and parents as the intended customers of the product, how to make the product distinctive and creative to attract consumers to buy it? Product creativity generally develops in three dimensions (see figure 4) :

(1) Product function: refers to the specificity of this product. 职能, which is the overall function or use of the product. Corresponding to the function of the school, who does the school train? Higher vocational colleges mainly train high-skilled and application-oriented professionals who meet the front-line needs of enterprise production, construction, service and management. (2) Product quality: refers to the sum of features and characteristics of this product that meet the use needs and potential needs. Corresponding to the education quality of the school, the focus should be on the quality of personnel training, including teaching, management, service and environment. 1) In terms of teaching and educating people, higher vocational colleges should focus on the school-running purpose of "helping students to become talents", further change the view of education and talents, and change from teacher-centered to student-centered, student-achievement-oriented, fully implement moral education into the classroom, and take all kinds of quality activities as carriers to carry out moral education throughout teaching activities, such as holding all kinds of ball games and autumn sports meetings; "National Day" and "New Year's Day" cultural evenings; Various professional skills competitions and other activities^[6]. 2) In terms of management and education: on the one hand, we should establish the concept of student-oriented education; On the other hand, it is necessary to explore ways and systems of professional education, including exploring ways and systems of professional education, improving the art of educating people by managers, striving to improve the art of using language and characters, the art of coordinating multiple management roles, and the art of strengthening education effects, etc., so as to creatively carry out management education and effectively improve the awareness and ability of management education^[7]. 3) In terms of service education: on the one hand, strengthen the awareness of service education of counselors and logistics personnel, carry out post ideological and political work, and transform themselves from being only a server to an educator, so as to enhance the awareness of educators and improve their ability to educate people. On the one hand, build an information service education platform, cooperate with various departments, and provide logistics services for students at the first time; At the same time, give full play to autonomous management's ability, encourage and guide students to actively participate in service education; Finally, we should establish and gradually optimize the school service education mechanism, truly grasp the growth needs of students, and educate and guide students among caring for people, helping people and serving people^[8]. 4) Environmental education: Education, as a social activity, always exists under a certain "environment". As far as school education is concerned, the group ecosystem (i.e., school environment) is undoubtedly the key to connect the whole with the individual and directly interact with the educated subjects. Whether or not to create an idealized group ecosystem (i.e., school environment) fundamentally determines the degree of realization of teaching and education goals, and also determines the school-running level and education quality of a school [9] In order to combine industry closely, the introduction of corporate culture into campus and classroom reflects the core characteristics of the professional environment and bears the main function of enterprise education. Under the background of integration of production and education and cooperation between schools and enterprises, in order to implement the fundamental task of cultivating people by virtue and achieve high-quality development, higher vocational colleges need to mobilize the strength of both schools and enterprises, optimize the education environment in all directions and strengthen the environment education in the whole process^[9].

(3) Product style: refers to the appearance and image of the product, such as the shape, style, color and so on. Corresponding to the high-quality employment of school graduates, what quality graduates can be trained and exported by higher vocational colleges? It is the first place for employment and people's livelihood, where people's hearts rest. It is estimated that the total number of college graduates nationwide in 2021 will be 9.09 million^[9]. Private higher vocational colleges make use of flexible management mechanism to create employment characteristics. 1) Establish a number of high-quality employment bases and train a number of graduates with industry characteristics, cultural identity, professional counterparts and technical recognition by means of information technology, open source and expand jobs and joint training; 2) Excavate the resources of outstanding alumni and industry associations, explore the employment market through various channels, and comprehensively improve the employment quality; Strengthen employment services and train a group of graduates who are employable, sustainable and able to study independently^[10].

Fig. 4 Product mapping school function

2. "Channel-based" creativity

In the process of enrollment marketing, private higher vocational colleges must innovate the enrollment mode, so as to promote the enrollment work more effectively. In addition to maintaining the publicity and enrollment information released by official website, it can also be publicized by means of new media webcast and Q&A. We must think about problems from the perspective of consumers, understand the social software and platforms that students and parents often use, increase publicity efforts, and further reach out to students and parents through online+offline publicity mode, so as to provide professional and reliable application answers for a period of time, so as to further improve the effect of enrollment publicity. The ultimate goal of channel creativity is only two: first, to discover the consumer demand of products, and second, to facilitate the purchase of consumers; Corresponding to the ultimate two purposes of higher vocational colleges: first, to find out the school selection needs of students and parents; second, to facilitate students and parents to apply for admission. Common enrollment channels include the following categories:

(1) College entrance examination students. This is one of the main channels for school enrollment. The provinces with large natural population growth and large net population inflow also have relatively large number and proportion of enrollment. At the same time, it is also the main channel for private higher vocational colleges to select talented students. (2) Individual enrollment. That is, the directional individual enrollment of higher vocational colleges for ordinary high school graduates and graduates of secondary vocational schools (including technical schools) has gradually occupied an important part of the enrollment of higher vocational colleges. Among them, if we can reduce the dropout rate of secondary vocational school students and provide students to higher vocational colleges steadily and continuously, it will also help higher vocational colleges to complete the enrollment work^[11]. (3) Conduct a special examination for qualified social workers such as aspiring youth, retired soldiers, laid-off workers, migrant workers, new professional farmers, etc. who are registered in Hunan Province or work in Hunan. For individual veterans and new-type professional farmers, the cultural quality test can be exempted, and vocational skill test related to the major to be applied for can be adopted. Through various enrollment channels such as individual enrollment, independent enrollment, comprehensive evaluation enrollment, school-enterprise cooperation oriented training, skill level application system, skill assessment system, etc., the channels for non-senior three students such as migrant workers and laid-off workers to enter higher vocational colleges can be opened. At the same time, each admissions institution should comprehensively consider the planning arrangement, professional training requirements and candidates' scores, and determine the admission criteria by classification to ensure that candidates who are willing to go to school and meet the basic training requirements can be admitted. (4) Employees in the industry are potential students. Combined with the characteristics of private higher vocational colleges, which are mostly run by enterprises or closely combined with industries, mature skilled talents with existing rank evaluation needs in various enterprises can be guided to attend higher vocational colleges, so as to obtain the learning that meets the job title evaluation and job promotion. From this point of view, it is another important potential student source for higher vocational colleges to encourage employees in specific industries to attend higher vocational colleges^[12].

4.2 School external marketing stimulation, expanding brand influence

1. "Partner-type" creative alliance of private higher vocational colleges to form a joint force to standardize the enrollment behavior of private higher vocational colleges.

(1) Private higher vocational colleges should strengthen the standardization of enrollment. Emphasizing "sunshine enrollment", we should strictly abide by the national enrollment system, and carry out the corresponding enrollment marketing work in a fair, just and open way, so as to fully guarantee the standardization and fairness of enrollment in private higher vocational colleges.

(2) Cooperation and competition among teams within the school.

Private higher vocational colleges should strengthen and supervise the standardization of enrollment.

2. "Publicity-oriented" creativity Establish brand management team, plan all kinds of product promotion activities, and always empower students.

In the enrollment process of private higher vocational colleges, we must do a good job in the corresponding top-level design, make reasonable arrangements and make active preparations, so as to ensure the smooth progress of enrollment marketing. When publicizing the enrollment work, private higher vocational colleges must combine the school-running characteristics and avoid homogenization competition, so as to better integrate with the development trend of the education market economy, and further deepen the methods of enrollment marketing through reform and innovation, so that schools can achieve better results in the enrollment marketing process.

(1) Establish the school's own characteristic brand publicity force and system, reserve key personnel who are familiar with marketing and management, and regularly push to various media platforms and parent groups according to the school's various activity levels, so as to continuously improve the school's brand influence.

(2) Reasonable packaging of the image of the school, multi-channel and multi-media linkage mechanism, shaping the brand image of the industry. Through online websites, WeChat official account, Tik Tok, video, Weibo, WeChat, the exposure and dissemination rate of various publications and media such as IP, campus culture, newspapers and brochures in offline schools, online and offline multi-channel and multi-media linkage communication will be realized, and finally the brand awareness of schools will be established and enhanced.

(3) Establish private higher vocational colleges' own school-running ideas and visions. Build the foundation of school brand from many aspects such as school mission, vision, teaching style, study style, campus culture, etc., and subtly pass it on to all teachers and students in daily management and teaching, so that all school staff and brand can be integrated, and the recognition and loyalty of employees, parents and students to the school can be improved.

5. summary

(1) Strengthen the construction of enrollment team in private higher vocational colleges. Private higher vocational colleges must strengthen their own team building, and organize an enrollment team with faith, execution and hardship. The team should take care of the overall situation, obey the arrangement, and each enrollment staff should be familiar with and master the relevant enrollment policies and strategies, and have a full understanding of the actual situation of the school, so as to better introduce the school to parents and candidates in the enrollment process. In addition, the enrollment personnel themselves should have good psychological quality and interpersonal communication skills, and can customize personalized publicity programs according to the needs of candidates and parents, so as to better complete the high-quality enrollment work. Continue to strengthen the connotation construction of the enrollment team, innovate the publicity methods of enrollment work, and refuse to be simple, exaggerated, and send head fees, etc., which can greatly promote the transformation of school enrollment publicity work to a benign direction.

(2) Establish a reward mechanism for enrollment in private higher vocational colleges. Some teachers and students who have made outstanding achievements in the enrollment work can be rewarded accordingly, which will encourage them to further the enrollment work to a certain extent.

(3) Attach great importance to it, increase the depth and breadth of enrollment publicity, and let enrollment information be transmitted to students and parents in multiple frequencies, channels and ways. In addition to the enrollment information of traditional paper media, TV media and interpersonal media, combined with new media means such as contemporary WeChat and Tik Tok, different media combinations are adopted in different periods to give full play to the best advantages of information dissemination, so that consumers can receive the information of the school at the first time and generate purchase desire.

China's economy has changed from a high-speed growth stage to a high-quality development stage, and all walks of life are in a critical period of development mode transformation and production change, among which the structural contradiction between the demand and supply of high-quality technical and skilled talents is particularly prominent, so it is urgent to speed up the development of modern vocational education and provide skilled talents support for promoting economic and social development and improving national competitiveness. Private higher vocational colleges, as a new thing in China's higher education system reform, are the main force

in the popularization stage of China's higher education. To treat students as "consumers" in schools, we should pay attention to the different needs of buyers (students and parents), show the advantages and highlights of our own products, adopt precise marketing methods, let "consumers" choose and "buy" themselves, and carry out various services after purchase.

Marketing is just a means. The cost performance of the product itself is an important factor for consumers to consider whether to buy or not. The comprehensive strength of the school is directly related to parents' goodwill. It is an important means to attract students by imparting strong skills and finding a decent job. Pay attention to the pain points of students and parents, create the effect of word-of-mouth communication, and constantly improve the school brand and connotation construction. The future enrollment strategy of high-quality private higher vocational colleges in the new era should be to explore the basic laws of the future education market economy, provide reference educational ideas, educational governance models, lifelong learning for students, and help poor students and migrant workers.

The success of "consumers" promotes the modernization of China's vocational education.

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